

ISic1277

I.Sicily inscription 1277

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. θή[κη]

2. Ἄρτεμ[---]

3. καὶ τοῦ [---]

4. οὐ αὐτοῦ [---]

5. εὐπλ[---]

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491445

EDCS 39101646

PHI 140766

PHI 175598

PHI 329722

PHI 330069

Bibliography

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